

From Epidural Hematoma to the Diagnosis of Primary Hyperaldosteronism: A Clinical Challenge. Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Primary hyperaldosteronism (PAH) is defined as a syndrome in which increased and autonomous aldosterone secretion originates from the adrenal gland. PAH is understood from a physiological perspective, where aldosterone regulatory mechanisms are unable to limit its various effects and clinical manifestations resulting from its ectopic overproduction. In the absence of angiotensin II, proximal tubular sodium reabsorption decreases, inducing a high flow of urine and sodium to the aldosterone-sensitive distal nephron. This induces an increase in sodium reabsorption mediated by epithelial sodium channels, resulting in secondary arterial hypertension. Several mutations, such as KCNJ5, present in adrenal adenomas that lead to PAH, have been identified. The case of a patient diagnosed with resistant arterial hypertension is presented. It is essential to consider other etiologies of secondary arterial hypertension. He was sent to the hospital floor where he presented neurological symptoms related to headache and drowsiness, remaining awake, without symptoms of intracranial hypertension or paresis in any body segment. It was decided to expand complementary studies due to suspicion of secondary arterial hypertension, with abdominal and pelvic tomography with bilateral adrenal growth, predominantly on the left side. Right testicle with approximate dimensions of 67X53MM, as a probable primary neoplasia. Testicular tumors occur mainly in patients with congenital adrenal hyperplasia, one of the most common congenital adrenal diseases, it belongs to the autosomal disorders of the adrenal cortex receptors that affect the production of adrenal steroids and is caused by a defect in one of the enzymes involved in adrenal steroidogenesis. The above was considered in our patient, however, the diagnosis was not completed because he refused to undergo oophorectomy or biopsy to determine the histology of the tumor. The importance of suspecting secondary causes of high blood pressure, regardless of the patient's initial diagnosis, is to perform the necessary diagnostic tests to confirm or rule out a diagnosis.

KEYWORDS: Epidural hematoma, hyperaldosteronism, testicular tumor.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
30 June 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Primary hyperaldosteronism (PAH) is defined as a syndrome in which increased and autonomous aldosterone secretion originates from the adrenal gland [1]. It manifests as clinical and biochemical alterations such as sodium retention and arterial hypertension, and even manifests changes in the cardiovascular system if not identified promptly. Aldosterone is known as a regulator of blood pressure, electrolyte balance, and volume, playing an important role in the regulation of the

renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) [2]. PAH is understood from a physiological perspective, where aldosterone regulatory mechanisms are unable to limit its various effects and clinical manifestations resulting from its ectopic overproduction. The initial lesion is the development of one or more sites of autonomous aldosterone secretion in one or both adrenal glands. Therefore, aldosterone secretion is independent of renin and angiotensin II. It often occurs in the context of hypokalemia, which would otherwise suppress

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aldosterone secretion. A simple head CT scan revealed a left subdural hematoma, leading to surgery, with a left craniotomy and drainage of the hematoma using a trephine. The patient was classified as an acute subdural hematoma with drainage of approximately 60 ml.

In the absence of angiotensin II, proximal tubular sodium reabsorption decreases, inducing a high flow of urine and sodium to the aldosterone-sensitive distal nephron. This induces an increase in sodium reabsorption mediated by epithelial sodium channels and, in return, to maintain the electroneutrality of the urinary lumen, this is where the increased excretion of potassium and hydrogen ions occurs, resulting in isotonic volume expansion and glomerular hyperfiltration, thus explaining the mechanism by which arterial hypertension secondary to hyperaldosteronism occurs. (3) Currently, two entities are recognized as causes of PAH: aldosterone-producing adrenal adenoma and bilateral adrenal hyperplasia, the latter being the purpose of our case presentation.

Some mutations present in adrenal adenomas that lead to PAH have been identified, such as KCNJ5, which encodes the inward rectifying potassium channel Kir 3.4. A mutation, G151R, allows the passage of K⁺ through the channel and blocks the passage of Na⁺ and CYP11B2, among others [4]. The main clinical manifestation of patients with PAH is arterial hypertension, which is resistant, which is characterized by remaining elevated above the target goal despite the use of at least three antihypertensives of different classes, including a long-acting calcium channel blocker, a renin-angiotensin system blocker or angiotensin receptor blocker, and a diuretic. All agents should be administered at maximum or maximally tolerated doses and with the appropriate dosing frequency [5] [6] [7]. In a patient diagnosed with resistant arterial hypertension, it is essential to consider other etiologies of secondary arterial hypertension, regardless of the clinical context in which they are found, this is where our clinical case becomes relevant.

CLINICAL CASE

A 17-year-old male with a history of head trauma secondary to a motorcycle accident presented the following symptoms upon arrival: oppressive headache, intensity 10/10, sudden

onset of holocranial pain, with decreased level of consciousness. Blood pressure was documented averaging 200/120 mmHg persistently, so the use of antihypertensive medication was not initially decided due to a possible response to the head trauma. Physical examination revealed generalized dullness on abdominal percussion except for the epigastrium and mesogastrium. A painful bilateral mass was observed on the right genital area, with increased volume and no apparent color changes. Osteotendinous reflexes were ++/++++, and both lower limbs were edematous. A simple cranial tomography was performed, which reported a left subdural hematoma, for which the patient underwent surgery, a left craniotomy was performed and the hematoma was drained by a trephine. The patient was classified as acute subdural hematoma with drainage of approximately 60 ml at high pressure, as well as a tear of the meningeal artery in different segments. No fracture was documented. The patient was sent to the hospital floor where he presented with neurological symptoms related to headache and drowsiness, remaining awake, without symptoms of intracranial hypertension or paresis in any body segment. During his hospital stay, given the persistence of an average blood pressure of 190/110 mmHg, it was decided to start treatment with losartan and nifedipine, which was not controlled in the first 7 days, so it was decided to add hydrochlorothiazide, continuing with arterial hypertension. As a pediatric patient, he was staged in percentile > 99th percentile. Laboratory tests: Hemoglobin 14.1 g/dL, Hct 41.7%, Leu 15.3 mg/uL, Neu 12.2 mg/uL, PlaQ 203 mg/uL, Fasting Glucose 70 mg/dL, Urea 19 mg/dL, Creatinine 0.54 mg/dL, Chlorine 105 mmol/L, Sodium 140 mmol/L, Potassium 2.5 mmol/L, Phosphorus 2.5 mg/dL, Magnesium 1.42 mg/dL, Calcium 8.2 mg/dL, Random Urinary Electrolytes: Urinary Sodium 129 mmol/L, Urinary Potassium 45.7 mmol/L, Urinary Chlorine 190 mmol/L, Blood Gas pH 7.53, pCO₂ 37 mmHg, pO₂ 83 mmHg, Bicarbonate 33 mEq/L, Lactate 0.3 mmol/L, transtubular potassium gradient 13.66. It was decided to extend complementary studies due to suspicion of secondary arterial hypertension, with abdominal and pelvic tomography with bilateral adrenal enlargement, predominantly on the left (Figures 1 and 2). Right testicle with approximate dimensions of 67X53MM, as a probable primary neoplasia.

Figure 1

A) Simple phase thoracoabdominal pelvic tomography, coronal section, soft tissue window, right renal fossa in its upper pole an image of hypodense triangular morphology of soft tissues without mass effect; likewise, in the contralateral renal fossa an image is observed in the upper pole with crescent morphology with soft tissue density without the presence of mass effect corresponding to bilateral adrenal hyperplasia. B) Abdominal tomography, simple phase axial section, soft tissue window at the level of the T12 vertebral body, upper pole of both renal fossae the same image previously described, observing both lesions without the presence of contact with adjacent organs liver (right renal fossa) and spleen (left renal fossa).

Figure 2

Figure 2: Simple phase coronal CT scan of the thoracoabdominal and pelvic tissues, showing hyperdensity in the right testicle, approximately 6.7 x 5.3 cm in size, heterogeneous with moderate hydrocele. The image is compatible with probable seminoma of the right testicle.

Figure 3

Figure 3: Chest CT scan, simple phase axial cut, showing grade III cardiomegaly, biventricular, right predominance.

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Germ cell tumor markers with AFP 5 ng/mL and HCG < 0.1 mIU/mL. Electrocardiogram Sinus Rhythm with Incomplete Left Bundle Branch Block with Hypertensive Heart Disease Lewis 13 mV Sokolow Lyon index 5.7 mV.

Figure 4

Figure 4: Echocardiogram Parasternal long axis, Measurement of the left ventricular outflow tract, Left Ventricular Diastolic diameter 4.6cm, Systolic diameter 2.5cm, LVEF: 65%, Interventricular septum thickness: 1.7cm, Posterior wall thickness: 1.5cm, Left ventricular mass: 183 gr/m². Right ventricle: 3.27cm, Mitral velocity: f wave velocity: 53/s, A wave velocity: 50/s, E/A ratio: 1.32, Aorta: 2.9cm, Left atrium: 2.9cm, PSAP: 21 mmHg. Concentric hypertrophy, LVEF 65%, left ventricular diastolic dysfunction GI, PSAP: 21 mmHg.

Finally, the result of plasma renin with a value of < 0.5 micro IU / ml and aldosterone 277 ng / dl was obtained, so a diagnosis of primary hyperaldosteronism was integrated, so it was decided to change the treatment strategy to Nifedipine 30 mg every 12 hours and spironolactone 50 mg every 24 hours, the patient was sent home and attended follow-up after a month where an average blood pressure of 130/70 mmHg was documented. Antihypertensive treatment was continued for 6 months, remaining asymptomatic and with blood pressure figures in the percentile between p95-p99, a genetic study was received with positivity for the KCNJ5 gene corresponding to familial primary hyperaldosteronism type III.

DISCUSSION

We present the case of a male in his second decade of life diagnosed with PAH, which causes resistant arterial hypertension, or formerly known as malignant hypertension, presenting elevated aldosterone levels, due to bilateral adrenal hyperplasia, one of the causes of PAH. Forty to five hundred percent of PAH cases are unilateral, with resistant hypertension accounting for 17 to 23% according to the European Society of Hypertension. Of these, only 1 to 10% are due to adrenal incidentalomas [8].

PAH corresponds to an inappropriate elevation of aldosterone for the natremia state, with autonomous aldosterone production independent of the RAAS, and a lack of suppression of aldosterone production in response to sodium

overload, resulting from aldosterone-induced reabsorption. Side effects include arterial hypertension with cardiovascular damage, sodium retention, as well as suppression of renin concentrations and increased potassium excretion, leading to hypokalemia [9].

In our patient, clinical suspicion began, in accordance with the literature, with resistant grade II or III hypertension in patients under 40 years of age, with biochemical findings such as metabolic alkalosis with hypokalemia, thus broadening the diagnostic spectrum. The transtubular potassium gradient was calculated, which is typically expected to be greater than 6, which leads us to infer that the renal response is appropriate to hypokalemia induced by increased aldosterone levels [10].

It is important to consider that although the diagnosis may have been initially delayed, the disiological response to head trauma should be taken into account. When cerebral blood flow is compromised, the sympathetic nervous system response generates systemic vasoconstriction to increase blood pressure, aiming to maintain cerebral perfusion pressure. However, when systolic pressures exceed 180 mmHg, blood pressure control is suggested, since negative effects such as cerebral edema are present [11]. The INTERACT2 study showed pressure targets of 110-139 versus 140-179 mmHg, without demonstrating differences in mortality or disability [12]. However, given the negative effects of maintaining elevated blood pressure, it was decided

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to start antihypertensive treatment 72 hours after admission. The patient's progression proved resistant to treatment with calcium channel blockers, angiotensin II receptor antagonists, and thiazide diuretics at maximum doses. Therefore, an approach to secondary causes of hypertension was required. A confirmed diagnosis requires a plasma aldosterone concentration, which must be greater than 20 ng/dL, and a plasma renin concentration, which is expected to be suppressed in the biochemical stage of hypokalemia [13]. When the above criteria are not met as described in the literature and a high suspicion exists, other confirmatory tests are described, such as the fludrocortisone suppression test, oral sodium tolerance test, intravenous saline tolerance test, and the captopril challenge test. Regarding the diagnosis by location, ideally, magnetic resonance imaging or computed tomography is suggested, and even adrenal vein catheterization [14]. In our patient, it was decided to perform an adrenal computed tomography with the initial objective of ruling out findings suggestive of adrenal carcinoma. We found bilateral adrenal hyperplasia in the absence of adenomas, this being, as we mentioned, a cause of PAH, so the diagnosis of PAH secondary to bilateral adrenal hyperplasia was established at that time. Although the literature recommends, in addition to performing adrenal tomography or adrenal resonance, complementing it with adrenal vein catheterization with the objective of lateralization mainly in unilateral lesions and in the case of bilateral adrenal hyperplasia to determine if aldosterone production is bilateral or unilateral, having greater recommendation in patients over 35 years of age, or bilateral adrenal nodules, so it was not considered part of the location diagnosis and there is no access in our center, so it was not performed. [15]

Surgical treatment by adrenalectomy was not chosen since the treatment for bilateral adrenal hyperplasia is pharmacological according to the British and Irish Society [16]. We decided to start treatment with Spironolactone which is considered the treatment of choice with a reduction in systolic blood pressure by 25% and diastolic by 22% with an initial dose of 50 to 400 mg/day. The side effect of the use of spironolactone is known as gynecomastia, however it is known that it is dose-dependent, reporting an incidence after 6 months of 6.9% with a dose of 50 mg/day and 52% with a dose of 150 mg/day [17]. Our patient, during a 9-month follow-up, did not report any gynecomastia, so treatment was continued with nifedipine 60 mg every 12 hours and spironolactone 50 mg every 12 hours, maintaining average blood pressures of 135/80 mmHg.

Testicular tumors occur primarily in patients with congenital adrenal hyperplasia, one of the most common congenital adrenal diseases. It belongs to the autosomal recessive adrenal cortex receptor disorders that affect adrenal steroid production and is caused by a defect in one of the enzymes involved in adrenal steroidogenesis. This was considered in our patient, however, the diagnosis was not completed

because he refused to undergo oophorectomy or biopsy to determine the histology of the tumor [18].

Conclusion

The importance of suspecting secondary causes of high blood pressure, regardless of the patient's initial diagnosis, and performing the necessary diagnostic tests to confirm or rule out a diagnosis.

REFERENCES

- I. Vedere T, Khalifa M. Hiperaldoesteronismo primario: Una revisión exhaustiva de la fisiopatología, el diagnóstico y el tratamiento. *Urol Clin North Am.* 2025;52(2):205–16.
- II. Bioletto, F.; Bollati, M.Lopez, C.; Arata, S.; Procopio, M. Ponzetto, F.; Ghigo, E.; Maccario, M.; Parasiliti-Caprino, M. Primary Aldosteronism and Resistant Hypertension: A Pathophysiological Insight. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2022, 23, 4803.
- III. Vaidya, A., Mulatero, P., Baudrand, R., & Adler, G. K. (2018). The expanding spectrum of primary aldosteronism: Implications for diagnosis, pathogenesis, and treatment. *Endocrine Reviews*, 39(6), 1057–1088.
- IV. Scholl, U. I. (2022). Genetics of primary aldosteronism. *Hypertension*, 79(5), 887–897.
- V. Camafort, M., Kreutz, R., & Cho, M.-C. (2024). Diagnosis and management of resistant hypertension. *Heart (British Cardiac Society)*, 110(22), 1336–1342.
- VI. Acelajado, M. C., Hughes, Z. H., Oparil, S., & Calhoun, D. A. (2019). Treatment of resistant and refractory hypertension. *Circulation Research*, 124(7), 1061–1070.
- VII. Carey, R. M., Calhoun, D. A., Bakris, G. L., Brook, R. D., Daugherty, S. L., Dennison-Himmelfarb, C. R., Egan, B. M., Flack, J. M., Gidding, S. S., Judd, E., Lackland, D. T., Laffer, C. L., Newton-Cheh, C., Smith, S. M., Taler, S. J., Textor, S. C., Turan, T. N., White, W. B., & American Heart Association Professional/Public Education and Publications Committee of the Council on Hypertension; Council on Cardiovascular and Stroke Nursing; Council on Clinical Cardiology; Council on Genomic and Precision Medicine; Council on Peripheral Vascular Disease; Council on Quality of Care and Outcomes Research; and Stroke Council. (2018). Resistant hypertension: Detection, evaluation, and management: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Hypertension*, 72(5), e53–e90.
- VIII. Araujo-Castro, M., Pascual-Corrales, E., Ortiz-Flores, A., & Escobar-Morreale, H. F. (2024). Hiperaldoesteronismo primario. *Medicine*, 14(13), 727–737.

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- IX. Araujo-Castro, Marta, & Parra-Ramírez, P. (2022). Diagnóstico del hiperaldosteronismo primario. *Medicina Clinica*, 158(9), 424–430.
- X. Choi, M. J., & Ziyadeh, F. N. (2008). The utility of the transtubular potassium gradient in the evaluation of hyperkalemia. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology: JASN*, 19(3), 424–426.
- XI. Krishnamoorthy, V., Chaikittisilpa, N., Kiatchai, T., & Vavilala, M. (2017). Hypertension after severe traumatic brain injury: Friend or foe? *Journal of Neurosurgical Anesthesiology*, 29(4), 382–387.
- XII. Anderson CS, Heeley E, Huang Y, Wang J, Stapf C, Delcourt C, et al. Rapid blood-pressure lowering in patients with acute intracerebral hemorrhage. *N Engl J Med* [Internet]. 2013;368(25):2355–65.
- XIII. Funder JW, Carey RM, Mantero F, Murad MH, Reincke M, Shibata H, et al. The management of primary aldosteronism: Case detection, diagnosis, and treatment: An endocrine society clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2016; 101:1889-916.
- XIV. Turcu AF, Yang J, Vaidya A. Primary aldosteronism - a multidimensional syndrome. *Nat Rev Endocrinol* [Internet]. 2022;18(11):665–82.
- XV. Funder JW, Carey RM, Mantero F, Murad MH, Reincke M, Shibata H, et al. The management of primary aldosteronism: Case detection, diagnosis, and treatment: An Endocrine Society clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* [Internet]. 2016;101(5):1889–916.
- XVI. Faconti L, Kulkarni S, Delles C, Kapil V, Lewis P, Glover M, et al. Diagnosis and management of primary hyperaldosteronism in patients with hypertension: a practical approach endorsed by the British and Irish Hypertension Society. *J Hum Hypertens* [Internet]. 2024;38(1):8–18.
- XVII. Jeunemaitre X, Chatellier G, Kreft-Jais C, Charru A, DeVries C, Plouin PF, et al. Efficacy and tolerance of spironolactone in essential hypertension. *Am J Cardiol* [Internet]. 1987;60(10):820–5.
- XVIII. Engels M, Span PN, van Herwaarden AE, Sweep FCGJ, Stikkelbroeck NMML, Claahsen-van der Grinten HL. Testicular adrenal rest tumors: Current insights on prevalence, characteristics, origin, and treatment. *Endocr Rev* [Internet]. 2019;40(4):973–87.